

COST OF CULTIVATION OF SEED PRODUCTION OF CHICKPEA IN WASHIM DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

Rutuja Patil*, V K Khobarkar** R D Vaidkar** and N V Shende***

*PG student **Asstt Professor

*** Professor & Head, Deptt of Agril Econ & Stat, Dr PDKV Akola

PGI, DR PDKV Akola, Maharashtra, India.

MS Received: 11.06.2025; MS Revised:08.07.2025; MS Accepted:09.07.2025)

MS 3407

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS)

Abstract

The average per hectare net return received at cost C_3 by the small medium and large Chickpea growers was Rs 44092.53, Rs. 50270.46 and Rs. 54288.36 respectively and at overall growers the net returns was Rs. 90011.06 The output-input ratio at cost C_3 for small, medium and large growers was 1.48, 1.58 and 1.60 respectively. At overall the output-input ratio was 1.57. The input output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and it indicated that the chickpea registered a good input output ratio i.e. 1.57 is indicated that Chickpea is a profitable crop.

Keyword: Chickpea, cost of cultivation

Introduction

In term of area and production Chickpea is most important pulse crop of India widely grown for centuries and accounts for nearly 40 per cent of the total pulse production in the country. India dominates in the global chickpea market as it has the distinction of being the largest producer, consumer and importer of chickpea in the world and accounts for over 64 per cent of the global output. India grows chickpea on about 13.5 million hectares area with 7.17 million tons of grains which represents more than 40 per cent of the national pulse acreage and production respectively. States like Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and Chhattisgarh together contribute more than 90 per cent of production from more than 90 per cent area.

India grows chickpea on about 104.71 lakh hectares area with 122.67 lakh tonnes and productivity is 1172 kg/ha of grains which represents more than 40 per cent of the national pulse acreage and production respectively. States like Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and Chhattisgarh together contribute more than 90 per cent of production from more than 90 per cent area.

Washim district of Vidarbha region of Maharashtra state was purposively selected for the present study.

The total area under pulses in Maharashtra was 49.94 lakh hectares with production 46.35 lakh tones and productivity 928 kg/ha respectively. Area under chickpea in Maharashtra during 2023-24 was 29.56 lakh hectares with an annual production of 31.78 lakh tonnes and average productivity of 1074 kg/ha. Area, Production and Productivity of chickpea in vidarbha was 7340.77 ha, 9601.47 tonnes and 1307.14 kg/ha respectively. The rural economy of Vidarbha is the basically the crop economy. The principal Kharif crops grown are cotton, soybean, jowar, tur, mung, sunflower etc.

In Washim district, area under chickpea was 820.35 hectares with production of 1109.93 tonnes and productivity of 1353.00 kg/ha during the year 2023-24. The area under cultivation of chickpea is increasing day by day and little work has been done on the economic aspects of them. For the seed production growers in Washim use varieties of chickpea such as JAKI-9218 PDKV Kanchan, PDKV Kanak, BG-10216 etc.

Objective:

To estimate the cost and returns of seed production of chickpea.

Methodology

To estimate the cost and returns of seed production of chickpea.

SN	Name of tahsils	Name of village	No. of Rabi onion growers
1	Risod	Vanoja	20
		Haral	20
		Motegaon	20
2	Malegaon	Selgaon	20
		Karangi	20
		Wagharud	20
		Total	120

Simple tabular analysis was used to accomplish the objective of present study. Standard cost concept was used to calculate the economics of chickpea seed production.

Result and Discussion

The share of each item's in total cost that is required for cost savings is provided. The basic cost ideas— cost A_1 , cost A_2 , cost B_1 , cost B_2 , cost C_1 , cost C_2 and cost C_3 , were used to determine the cost. Various cost concepts have varied research utilities. An attempt has been made to estimate the costs of seed production of chickpea crops in the research area, which are shown in the tables that follow.

Per hectare input utilization pattern of selected growers

To obtain highest yield it is necessary to make optimum use of inputs such as seed, fertilizers, human labour, bullock labour etc. Therefore, it is felt necessary to study on various levels of input used during crop production. The information regarding per hectare input utilization for black gram by selected farmers of different size group is presented in Table 1.

Table: 1. Per hectare input utilization pattern of selected farmers

Particulars	Unit	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
		Physical Qty.	Physical Qty.	Physical Qty.	Physical Qty.
Seed	Kg	78.36	77.08	80.48	78.61
Fertilizer					

It is observed from Table 1 that input utilization of seed production of Chickpea is less in medium and large growers than small. In case of small growers, the requirement of seed was 78.36 kg/ha, where as in medium and large it was 77.08 and 80.48 kg/ha. The use of N, P, K, S by small growers were 24.78, 45.97 and 11.30 kg/ha respectively where as in case of medium and large it was 25.22, 46.98, 13.54 kg/ha and 26.46, 47.98, 13.78 kg/ha.

The hired human labour requirements are more in case of large growers i.e. 43.69 and less in case of medium and small growers i.e. 34.10, 31.01 respectively. The more family labour work in case of large growers i.e. 22.33 as compared to medium and small growers i.e. 19.77, 18.18 respectively.

The utilization of machinery (Hrs.) per hectare was 10.85, 11.68, and 11.87 hrs for small, medium and large size group respectively and the overall level was 11.59 hrs. From this it was revealed that, in case of small growers use of machinery was comparatively less than medium and large growers.

N	Kg	24.78	25.22	26.46	25.48
P	Kg	45.97	46.98	47.88	46.94
K	Kg	11.30	13.54	13.78	12.87
Hired Human labour	Male	12.29	14.04	15.84	14.38
	Female	18.72	20.06	27.85	22.74
	Sub-Total	31.01	34.1	43.69	37.12
Family labour	Male	11.24	12.47	14.52	13.01
	Female	7.63	7.2	7.8	7.54
	Sub-total	18.18	19.77	22.33	20.56
Bullock Labour	Days	5.35	3.56	3.61	3.92
Machine	Hrs	10.85	11.68	11.87	11.59

Utilization of seed production chickpea of Small growers

The cost incurred by chickpea grower on practices, after fruiting of the crops for cultivation of crop is categorized as cost of cultivation. The

cost of cultivation included the expenses on various items viz., machine, seed and fertilizer, plant protection measures, irrigation charges etc.

Table: 2 Cost of cultivation of Chickpea for small growers (ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Input/ ha.	Cost/ Unit of input	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '
1	2	3			4	5	6
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	12.29	319.79	3930.21	4.24
		Female	Days	18.72	259.17	4851.58	5.24
		Total	Days	31.01	283.19	8781.79	9.48
2	Bullock Labour	Total	Days	5.35	712.16	3810.07	4.11
3	Machine charges	Total	Hrs	10.85	720.71	7819.67	8.44
4	Seed		Kg	78.36	113.98	8931.29	9.64
5	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	24.78	26.17	648.49	0.70
		P	Kg.	45.97	40.18	1847.07	1.99
		K	Kg.	11.3	45.56	514.82	0.56
		Total	Kg.	82.05	111.91	3010.38	3.25
6	Irrigation charges.	(Rs.)		0	0	2212.12	2.39
7	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				708.85	0.77
8	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				738.95	0.80
9	Plant Protection	(Rs.)				2234.81	2.41
10	Field Inspection charge	(Rs.)				500.23	0.54
11	Working Capital (1to10)	(Rs.)				38748.16	41.84
12	Interest on working Cap.	(Rs.)				774.9632	0.84
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)				5763.13	6.22
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				45	0.05
15	COST " A ₁ " (Item 11 to 14)	(Rs.)				45331.25	48.95
16	Rent paid for Leased in land				0	0	0.00
17	COST " A ₂ " (Item 15 to 16)					45331.25	48.95
18	Int. on Fix. Cap. @ 10%					10885.62	11.75
19	COST " B ₁ " (Item 15 to 18)					56216.87	60.71
20	Rental Value of owned Land	(Rs.)				22737.95	24.55
21	COST " B ₂ " (Item 19 to 20)					78954.83	85.26
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	11.24	303.93	3416.25	3.69
		Female	Days	7.63	237.93	1815.46	1.96
		Total	Days	18.18	287.77	5231.72	5.65
23	Cost " C ₁ " (Item 19 to 22)	(Rs.)				61448.58	66.36
24	Cost " C ₂ " (Item 21 to 22)	(Rs.)				84186.54	90.91
25	10% Cost " C ₂ "					8418.65	9.09
26	Cost " C ₃ " (Item 24 to 25)					92605.19	100.00
27	Yield main produce/ha	(Qtl)		20.82	6429.88	133870.08	
28	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Qtl)		11.35	249.13	2827.63	
29	Value of total produce	(Rs.)		32.17	4249.23	136697.72	
30	Per quintal cost of Prod.	(Rs.)				4435.92	

(Figures in parenthesis indicates the per cent to total)

Table 2 revealed that per hectare cost of cultivation of Chickpea for Rs. 4435.92/-. The major item was working capital i.e. 41.84 per cent

followed by, Seed 9.64 per cent, Hired Human Labour 9.48 per cent, Machine Charges 8.44 per cent Depreciation 6.22 per cent share to cost

C₃ respectively. The per cent share of Cost A₂ and Cost B₂ were 48.95 per cent and 85.26 per cent respectively in total cost. The per ha yield of main produce was 20.82 Quintal and per ha yield of by produce was 11.35 Quintal and gross value of total produce was Rs.136697.72. The per quintal cost of production was Rs. 4435.92.

Cost of cultivation of seed production Chickpea for Medium growers

Table 3 revealed that per hectare cost of cultivation of Chickpea for Rs.4130.67/-. The major item was working capital i.e. 45.28 per cent

followed by, hired human labour 11.13 per cent, Seed 10.16 per cent, Machine charge cost 9.29 per cent, Depreciation 5.72 per cent share to cost C₃ respectively. The per cent share of Cost A₂ and Cost B₂ were 51.96 per cent and 84.59 per cent respectively in total cost. The per ha yield of main produce was 21.01 Quintal and per ha yield of by produce was 12.30 Quintal and gross value of total produce was Rs137300.68. The per quintal cost of production was Rs.4130.67.

Table No: 3 Cost of cultivation of Chickpea for medium growers (ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Input/ ha.	Cost/ Unit of input	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '
1	2	3			4	5	6
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	14.04	319.54	4486.3	5.15
		Female	Days	20.06	259.36	5202.83	5.98
		Total	Days	34.1	284.14	9689.13	11.13
2	Bullock Labour	Total	Days	3.56	780.71	2779.34	3.19
3	Machine charges	Total	Hrs	11.68	692.57	8089.18	9.29
4	Seed		Kg	77.08	114.70	8840.88	10.16
5	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	25.22	27.64	697.08	0.80
		P	Kg.	46.98	43.59	2047.85	2.35
		K	Kg.	13.54	49.62	671.85	0.77
		Total	Kg.	85.74	120.84	3416.78	3.93
6	Irrigation charges.	(Rs.)				2065.09	2.37
7	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				818.24	0.94
8	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				896.43	1.03
9	Plant Protection	(Rs.)				2305.12	2.65
10	Field Inspection charge	(Rs.)				504.4	0.58
11	Working Capital (1to10)	(Rs.)				39404.59	45.28
12	Interest on working Cap.	(Rs.)				788.09	0.91
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)				4980.17	5.72
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				45	0.05
15	COST " A ₁ " (Item 11 to 14)	(Rs.)				45217.85	51.96
16	Rent paid for Leased in land					0	0.00
17	COST " A ₂ " (Item 15 to 16)					45217.85	51.96
18	Int. on Fix. Cap. @ 10%					5563.67	6.39
19	COST " B ₁ " (Item 15 to 18)					50781.52	58.35
20	Rental Value of owned Land	(Rs.)				22838.45	26.24
21	COST " B ₂ " (Item 19 to 20)					73619.97	84.59
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	12.47	304.49	3797.11	4.36
		Female	Days	7.2	286.29	1701.3	1.95
		Total	Days	19.77	978.11	5498.42	6.32
23	Cost " C ₁ " (Item 19 to 22)	(Rs.)				56279.93	64.67
24	Cost " C ₂ " (Item 21 to 22)	(Rs.)				79118.38	90.91
25	10% Cost " C ₂ "					7911.84	9.09
26	Cost " C ₃ " (Item 24 to 25)					87030.22	100.00
27	Yield main produce /ha	(Qtl)		21.01	6391.72	134290.08	
28	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Qtl)		12.3	244.76	3010.59	
29	Value of total produce	(Rs.)		33.31	4121.90	137300.68	
30	Per quintal cost of Prod.	(Rs.)				4130.67	

(Figures in parenthesis indicates the per cent to total)

Cost of cultivation of seed production of Chickpea for Large growers

Table No: 4 Cost of cultivation of Chickpea for Large growers (ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Input/ ha.	Cost/ Unit of input	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '
1	2	3			4	5	6
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	15.84	321.85	5098.16	5.68
		Female	Days	27.85	258.23	7191.76	8.01
		Total	Days	43.69	281.30	12289.93	13.69
2	Bullock Labour	Total	Days	3.61	686.89	2479.67	2.76

3	Machine charges	Total	Hrs	11.87	726.22	8620.27	9.61
4	Seed		Kg	80.48	112.65	9065.94	10.10
5	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	26.46	29.04	768.39	0.86
		P	Kg.	47.88	44.68	2139.27	2.38
		K	Kg.	13.78	50.35	693.82	0.77
		Total	Kg.	88.12	124.07	3601.48	4.01
6	Irrigation charges.	(Rs.)		0	0	2294.11	2.56
7	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				930.38	1.04
8	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				963.85	1.07
9	Plant Protection	(Rs.)				2676.47	2.98
10	Field Inspection charge	(Rs.)				512.56	0.57
11	Working Capital (1to10)	(Rs.)				43434.65	48.40
12	Interest on working Cap.	(Rs.)				868.69	0.97
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)				3142.78	3.50
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				45	0.05
15	COST " A ₁ " (Item 11 to 14)	(Rs.)				47491.12	52.92
16	Rent paid for Leased in land				0	0	0.00
17	COST " A ₂ " (Item 15 to 16)					47491.12	52.92
18	Int. on Fix. Cap. @ 10%					3783.45	4.22
19	COST " B ₁ " (Item 15 to 18)					51274.57	57.14
20	Rental Value of owned Land	(Rs.)				23969.91	26.70
21	COST " B ₂ " (Item 19 to 20)					75234.49	83.84
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	14.52	311.31	4520.29	5.04
		Female	Days	7.8	234.36	1828.05	2.04
		Total	Days	22.33	284.29	6348.35	7.07
23	Cost " C ₁ " (Item 19 to 22)	(Rs.)				57622.92	64.21
24	Cost " C ₂ " (Item 21 to 22)	(Rs.)				81582.84	90.91
25	10% Cost " C ₂ "					8158.28	9.09
26	Cost " C ₃ " (Item 24 to 25)					89741.12	100.00
27	Yield main produce/ha	(Qtl)		21.78	6448.77	140454.26	
28	Value of by-produce/ha.	(Qtl)		13.77	259.64	3575.21	
29	Value of total produce	(Rs.)		35.55	4051.46	144029.48	
30	Per quintal cost of Prod.	(Rs.)				4108.42	

(Figures in parenthesis indicates the per cent to total)

Table 4 revealed that per hectare cost of cultivation of Chickpea for Rs. 4108.42/-. The major item was working capital i.e. 48.40 per cent followed by, hired human labour 13.69 per cent, Seed 10.10 per cent, Machine Charges 9.61 per cent, Fertilizer 4.01 per cent share to cost C₃ respectively. The per cent share of Cost A₂ and Cost B₂ were 52.92 per cent and 83.84 per cent respectively in total cost. The per ha yield of main produce was 21.78 Quintal and per ha yield of by produce was 13.77 Quintal and gross value of total produce was Rs. 153609.76. The per quintal cost of production was Rs. 4108.42.

Cost of cultivation of seed production of Chickpea for Overall growers

Table No: 5 Cost of cultivation of Chickpea for Overall growers

(ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Input/ ha.	Cost/ Unit of input	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '
1	2	3			4	5	6
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	14.38	320.55	4609.51	5.20
		Female	Days	22.74	258.78	5884.72	6.63
		Total	Days	37.12	282.71	10494.24	11.83
2	Bullock Labour	Total	Days	3.92	644.70	2527.22	2.85
3	Machine charges	Total	Hrs	11.59	710.73	8237.32	9.28
4	Seed		Kg	78.61	113.77	8943.18	10.08
5	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	25.48	27.61	703.5	0.79
		P	Kg.	46.94	42.82	2009.97	2.27
		K	Kg.	12.87	48.51	624.32	0.70
		Total	Kg.	85.29	118.94	3337.79	3.76
6	Irrigation charges.	(Rs.)				2179.83	2.46
7	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				879.01	0.99
8	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				891.42	1.00

Table 5 revealed that per hectare cost of cultivation of Chickpea for Rs.4161.21/-. The major item was working capital i.e. 45.57 per cent followed by, Hired Human Labour 11.83 per cent, Seed 10.08 per cent, Machine Charges 9.28 per cent, Fertilizer 3.76 per cent share to cost C₃ respectively. The per cent share of Cost A₂ and Cost B₂ were 51.54 per cent and 84.41 per cent respectively in total cost. The per ha yield of main produce was 21.26 Quintal and per ha yield of by produce was 12.67 Quintal and gross value of total produce was Rs. 139720.69 The per quintal cost of production was Rs. 4161.21/-

9	Plant Protection	(Rs.)				2431.52	2.74
10	Field Inspection charge	(Rs.)				510.36	0.58
11	Working Capital (1to10)	(Rs.)				40431.88	45.57
12	Interest on working Cap.	(Rs.)				808.63	0.91
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)				4438.38	5.00
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				45	0.05
15	COST " A ₁ " (Item 11 to 14)	(Rs.)				45723.89	51.54
16	Rent paid for Leased in land					0	0.00
17	COST " A ₂ " (Item 15 to 16)					45723.89	51.54
18	Int. on Fix. Cap. @ 10%					5920.76	6.67
19	COST " B ₁ " (Item 15 to 18)					51644.65	58.21
20	Rental Value of owned Land	(Rs.)				23241.78	26.20
21	COST " B ₂ " (Item 19 to 20)					74886.44	84.41
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	13.01	307.15	3996.14	4.50
		Female	Days	7.54	234.89	1771.14	2.00
		Total	Days	20.56	280.50	5767.28	6.50
23	Cost " C ₁ " (Item 19 to 22)	(Rs.)				57411.93	64.71
24	Cost " C ₂ " (Item 21 to 22)	(Rs.)				80653.72	90.91
25	10% Cost " C ₂ "					8065.37	9.09
26	Cost " C ₃ " (Item 24 to 25)					88719.09	100.00
27	Yield main produce/ ha	(Qtl)		21.26	6422.04	136532.59	
28	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Qtl)		12.67	251.62	3188.08	
29	Value of total produce	(Rs.)		33.93	4117.91	139720.69	
30	Per quintal cost of Prod.	(Rs.)				4161.21	

(Figures in parenthesis indicates the per cent to total)

Per hectore Cost and Return from Chickpea seed production

The per ha cost and returns of Chickpea was workout for small, medium and large growers were presented in Table 6

Table 6 Economics of Chickpea cultivation (Rs/qtl)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Main Produce (q/ha)	20.82	21.01	21.78	21.26
2	Value of Main Produce	133870.08	134290.08	140454.26	136532.59
3	Value of By Produce	2827.63	3010.59	3575.21	3188.08
4	Gross return	136697.72	137300.68	144029.48	139720.69
5	Cost of cultivation at				
	Cost A ₁	45331.25	45217.85	47491.12	45723.89
	Cost A ₂	45331.25	45217.85	47491.12	45723.89
	Cost B ₁	56216.87	50781.52	51274.57	51644.65
	Cost B ₂	78954.83	73619.97	75234.48	74886.43
	Cost C ₁	61448.58	56279.93	57622.92	57411.93
	Cost C ₂	84186.54	79118.38	81582.83	80653.72
	Cost C ₃	92605.19	87030.22	89741.12	88719.09
6	Return at				
	Cost A ₁	91366.47	92082.83	96538.35	93996.79
	Cost A ₂	91366.47	92082.83	96538.35	93996.79
	Cost B ₁	80480.85	86519.16	92754.90	88076.03
	Cost B ₂	57742.89	63680.71	68794.99	64834.25
	Cost C ₁	75249.14	81020.75	86406.55	82308.75
	Cost C ₂	52511.18	58182.30	62446.64	59066.97
	Cost C ₃	44092.53	50270.46	54288.36	51001.60
7	Input Output Ratio at				
	Cost A ₁	3.02	3.04	3.03	3.06
	Cost A ₂	3.02	3.04	3.03	3.06
	Cost B ₁	2.43	2.70	2.81	2.71
	Cost B ₂	1.73	1.86	1.91	1.87
	Cost C ₁	2.22	2.44	2.50	2.43

Cost C ₂	1.62	1.74	1.77	1.73
Cost C ₃	1.48	1.58	1.60	1.57

It is revealed from table 6 that, the per hectare average yield for small, medium and large growers was 21.38 quintals, 20.69 quintals and 21.78 quintals respectively and the overall growers was 21.23 quintals indicating that the increasing in yield with the increase in size of land holdings of growers. The per quintal average rate were obtained was Rs 133870.08, Rs.134290.08 and Rs.140454.26 for small, medium and large growers respectively and overall, it was Rs 136532.59. The average gross returns were obtained was Rs 136697.72, Rs.137300.68 and Rs.144029.48 for small, medium and large growers respectively and overall, it was Rs. 139720.69. Whereas the cost of production at cost C₂ was of small, medium and large growers was Rs. 84186.54, Rs. 79118.38 and Rs. 81582.83 respectively and at overall growers the net returns was Rs. 80653.72.

Conclusion:

The average per hectare net return received at cost C₃ by the small medium and large Chickpea growers was Rs 44092.53, Rs. 50270.46 and Rs. 54288.36 respectively and at overall growers the net returns was Rs. 90011.06 The output-input ratio at cost C₃ for small, medium

and large growers was 1.48, 1.58 and 1.60 respectively. At overall the output-input ratio was 1.57. The input output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and it indicated that the chickpea registered a good input output ratio i.e. 1.57 is indicated that Chickpea is a profitable crop.

References

1. **Kumar, K., Yogi, V., Arya, S., & Kumar, D. (2022).** Comparative economics of chickpea production in Rajasthan with reference to Gangour variety. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, SP-11(2), 868–871.
2. **Sharma, S. K., & Deshmukh, M. K. (2021).** An economic analysis of seed production of chickpea in Kabirdham district of Chhattisgarh. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 16(10), 477–479.
3. **Shriram, P., Tevari, P., Vaishnavi, Lokesh, G. B., Deshmanya, J. B., & Kumar, V. K. (2023).** An economic analysis of rabi sorghum and chickpea seed production in Nek region. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 12(4), 2145–2150.